

A Study of the English Language Varieties, the Syllabus and the Classroom Instruction Realities in Nigerian Secondary Schools

Moses Olusanya Ayoola

*Department of Languages and Linguistics, Bamidele Olumilua University of Education,
Science and Technology, Ikere-Ekiti, Nigeria*

Mercy Adenike Bankole

*Department of Languages and Linguistics, Bamidele Olumilua University of Education,
Science and Technology, Ikere-Ekiti, Nigeria*

Adekunle Adegite

*Department of Languages and Linguistics, Bamidele Olumilua University of Education,
Science and Technology, Ikere-Ekiti, Nigeria*

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Abstract:

The teaching of English Language in Nigeria has always been modeled after British English (BE) being a former British colony which is the supposed ideal despite the reality of other varieties such as Nigerian English and American English while the examination bodies in Nigeria also remain very strict on the British English. This study investigates the variety of English being taught in Nigerian secondary schools using Ekiti state as a sample. The main objective of this study is to examine the variety of English recommended by the syllabus for teaching in Secondary schools vis a vis the variety being taught and used by the teachers and the effectiveness of the

teachers as models of proficiency in the target variety of English being taught. The total number of 100 secondary schools distributed across the 16 local government areas of Ekiti State, Nigeria were selected for this study. As such 100 teachers of English were selected randomly as source of data. Classroom observation and questionnaire together with a designed variety checklist were used to elicit information from the respondents. The result revealed evident discrepancy between claimed proficiency, preferred English variety, and actual classroom instruction practices. The findings of the study present a complex and intriguing scenario regarding teacher proficiency, classroom instruction, and the use of different English varieties. The study concludes that the standard stipulated by the syllabus seems to be unrealistic because the teachers don't have the proficiency in such variety to serve as role models and that there is need for acknowledging and integrating diverse English varieties, including Nigerian English, into syllabi and instructional strategies to better cater for the linguistic needs of students.

Keywords: *instruction, Nigerian English, realities, syllabus, Varieties.*

Introduction

The English language holds a paramount position in Nigeria, serving as a unifying tool for

its diverse populace and playing a pivotal role in education, communication, and socio-economic advancement of the country. The English

language acquisition is very important for all students as a stepping-stone for proficiency in other school subjects being the medium of instruction in schools. The knowledge of the language is needed by the students for all purposes- educational, economical and the national growth and development.

The importance of English language as a school subject is mainly determined by the utilitarian value it has in Nigerian society. English is the official language and language of administration, commerce and industry, science and technology, law and legal draft, etc. Given this scenario, Salami (2002) stressed the importance of use of English language in improving communication among the various ethnic groups in Nigeria. He therefore calls for a need to improve the quality of spoken and written English language among school children.

In recognition of the importance of English language in educational sector as well as its communication value among citizens, the government had made it a compulsory and core subject in schools (National Policy on Education, 2004). It is also mandatory for students to have a credit pass in English language before he/she could gain an admission into the university. This also gives the reason why many parents can do anything to see that their children make a credit pass or above in English language in terminal Examinations. This shows the importance or relevance of English language in Nigerian educational system.

In the context of Nigerian secondary schools, the English language syllabus and the classroom instruction practices significantly shape students' language proficiency, critical thinking abilities, and overall academic performance. Therefore, a comprehensive evaluation of the English language syllabus and its alignment with classroom instruction realities is essential to ensure that Nigerian students are adequately prepared to face the linguistic and intellectual challenges of the 21st century. This evaluative analysis aims to scrutinize the English language syllabus and shed light on the existing classroom instruction dynamics within Nigerian secondary

schools to identify potential gaps, strengths, and areas of improvement.

Literature Review

Babatunde (2002) states that the diversity of the English Language is a reality to be lived with and the multiple identities of English in the world is a factor of the linguistic, cultural and pragmatic implications of the context in which English functions. Igboanusi (2002) observes that “the real problem with the increasing use of English as a global language, particularly the spread of American influence in former British colonies, is the acceptable variety to be used in teaching and examining, between British English and American English”. He went further to state that the problem becomes even greater with the emergence of indigenized varieties of English in such countries. Corroborating the above view, Babatunde (2002) is of the view that Standard English is only an ideal, not a reality. Even if there was such a thing as Standard English in the past, it can no longer be found anywhere. It is fictive reality. Thus, there is a perceived problem in the English language pedagogy in Nigeria with the acclaimed British standard strictly recommended by the various examination bodies and syllabi and curricula.

In Nigeria, English language is a legacy of colonialism and it has become an indispensable second language (ESL) that everyone must learn or acquire for social mobility. It is the medium of instruction from secondary school to tertiary school and a teaching subject in primary school (Obayan(1991), Bamgbose (1968) and Akindele and Adegbite (1999). Thus, secondary school in Nigeria is a major educational level where English Language is learnt and taught as a major subject and as the medium of instruction. The teaching of English Language in Nigeria has always been modeled after British English (BE) being a former colony of British but there is also growing influence of American English (AME) due to economic influence of America; there is also the reality of a domesticated variety called Nigerian English (NE). These three varieties are in use in Nigeria today. However, the examination bodies in Nigeria remain very strict

on the British English as the standard which is supposed the ideal.

Reacting to the problem of English language teaching in Nigeria, Obanya (2002:204), observes that “in ideal situations there would be a perfect match between what is prescribed, what is practiced, and consequently what achieved (outcome) is”. It is expected of (ESL) learners in the Nigerian context to be competent in English in social contexts beyond the school system after about nine or more years of learning English and using it for instruction at the primary and secondary levels. Such individual is expected to perform excellently while using English for academic, linguistic and communicative purpose. However, the socio-linguistic realities, according to Obanya (2002:207), are different in that the situation at the secondary school level is that in which the learners’ motivation is geared towards *passing* English and *mastering* it).

Ola-Busari (2014) argues for the evaluation of English Language Teaching and Learning in Nigeria to support future national development based on the exploration of the state of teaching and learning English in both countries, the impediments that negate the ability of young people to succeed academically and to impact meaningfully on their countries’ sustainable development and a critical overview of English as the language of instruction and an appraisal of the implications of New Englishes in relation to standardization in second language classroom. The overall objective of language teaching generally is to create a capacity to communicate in the target languages of the learners. Unfortunately, many language activities in our language syllabi and textbooks run contrary to the true nature of communication. What should be considered most important is that the learners should be made to use the English language for the real communication purposes rather than the imposition of grammatical structures and meanings that are alienated from the learners’ social contexts or situations as well as the teacher’s self-made examples. The major concern of this study therefore, is to investigate the variety of English being taught in Nigerian secondary schools using Ekiti state as a sample.

Objectives of the study

This study examines the variety of English being taught in Nigerian secondary schools using Ekiti state as a sample. The main objective of this study is to examine the variety of English recommended by the syllabus for teaching in Secondary schools vis a vis the variety being taught and used by the teachers. The study also examines the effectiveness of the teachers as models of proficiency in the target variety of English being taught.

Methodology

A purposive random sampling was used to select a representative sample of 100 secondary schools from the 16 local government areas in Ekiti state. The study involves 100 English teachers, and 500 students (10 from each school) in Ekiti state Secondary schools. Structured questionnaires and variety checklist were given to the teachers to fill to assess the variety they used and their proficiency in the target variety of English. - Students also completed questionnaires to gather their perceptions and experiences regarding the English variety taught by their teachers. Syllabus documents and textbooks used in secondary schools were analyzed to identify the recommended variety of English. Classroom observations were conducted to assess the actual English variety being taught by teachers. Quantitative data from surveys and variety checklist were analyzed using statistical software. Qualitative data from interviews and textbook analysis were analyzed thematically to identify patterns and themes. The extent of variation between the recommended variety and the actual variety taught by teachers were assessed quantitatively. Proficiency levels of teachers were compared to the recommended standard. The results are presented by employing descriptive analysis and test of hypotheses such as frequency count, percentages, and correlation analysis and t-test statistic. While frequency count proffer answers to the items of the questionnaires given to the respondents in the

field, the correlation analysis and t-test statistic were used to test the hypotheses formulated at the 0.05 level of significance.

Analysis

Respondents' Demographic Characteristics

The responses of teachers to the items of the questionnaire were analyzed descriptively. The variables of consideration include teachers' gender, qualification, and English language variety indicators.

Table 1. Frequency and Percentage of Teachers' Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	44	44.0
Female	56	56.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 1 above shows the frequency and percentage of teachers' gender in secondary

schools in Ekiti state selected for study. The table indicates that 44 (44.0%) male teachers and 56 (56.0%) female teachers participated in the study.

Table 2. Frequency and Percentage of Teachers' Qualification

Qualification	Frequency	Percentage
M.A	2	2.0
M.Ed	2	2.0
B.A	18	18.0
B.Ed	74	74.0
NCE	4	4.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 2 above shows the frequency and percentage of teachers' qualification in secondary schools in Ekiti State selected for study. The table indicates that 2 (2.0%) teachers with M.A qualification, 2 (2.0%) teachers with M.Ed qualification, 18 (18.0%) teachers with B.A qualification, 74 (74.0%) teachers with B.Ed qualification and 4 (4.0%) teachers with NCE qualification participated in the study.

Research Question 1: What are the Varieties of English Language in Existence in Nigeria?

Table 3. Existence of Varieties of English Language in Nigeria

S/N	Listening sub-skills	YES	NO	Mean	SD	RMK
1.	Do you agree that there is a variety of English called Nigerian English?	100 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	1.00	0.00	YES
2.	Do you agree that Nigerian English is sub-standard to other varieties such as BSE and AmSE?	86 (86.0)	14 (14.0)	1.14	0.35	YES
3.	Do you agree with the claim that Nigerian English is nothing but outright Errors?	37 (37.0)	63 (63.0)	1.63	0.49	NO
4.	Do you believe in the reality of standard English?	95 (95.0)	5 (5.0)	1.05	0.22	YES
5.	Do you believe that British Standard can be realistic in this environment?	77 (77.0)	23 (23.0)	1.23	0.42	YES
6.	Do you demonstrate proficiency in Standard English pronunciation, grammar, and vocabulary?	95 (95.0)	5 (5.0)	1.05	0.22	YES
7.	Do you Provide accurate and appropriate language models for students?	83 (83.0)	17 (17.0)	1.17	0.38	YES

Note: Numbers in parenthesis indicate percentage

Table 3 above indicated that all of the participants (100.0%) that there is a variety of English called Nigerian English while none

disagreed (0.0%). The percentage of participants who agreed (86.0%) that Nigerian English is sub-standard to other varieties such as BSE and

AmSE was much larger than the percentage of those who disagreed (14.0%). A smaller percentage of respondents (37.0%) agreed with the claim that Nigerian English is nothing but outright errors while the majority (63.0%) of the teachers held a contrary opinion. The question “Do you believe in the reality of Standard English?” elicited 95.0% of agreement, a much larger percentage, compared to those who disagreed (5.0%). Similarly, a larger percentage (77.0%) of the participants believes that British Standard English can be realistic in this environment contrary to the opinion of 23.0% of the teachers who had different views. The percentage of teachers who believed that they

demonstrate proficiency in Standard English pronunciation, grammar, and vocabulary was 95.0% which is significantly higher than the 5.0% who indicated lack of proficiency. Interestingly, 83.0% teachers indicated that they provide accurate and appropriate language models for their students while 17.0% did not answer the question in the affirmative.

From the above, the existence of the three varieties of English (BrE, AmE and NigE) is confirmed and that the variety preferred by the syllabus and the examination bodies is British Standard English (BrE).

Research Question 2: What Variety of English is Recommended and Taught in Schools?

Table 4. The Variety of English Language Recommended and Taught in Schools

S/N	Item	BS	AE	NE	CO	Mean	SD	RMK
1.	Which Variety of English does the syllabus recommend for teaching?	88 (88.0)	2 (2.0)	10 (10.0)	0 (0.0)	1.22	0.61	BS
2.	Which Variety of English do you teach in the class?	90 (90.0)	10 (10.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1.20	0.60	BS
3.	Which Variety do the examination bodies examine?	87 (87.0)	1 (1.0)	12 (12.0)	0 (0.0)	1.25	0.66	BS
4.	Which Variety of English do you use outside the classroom?	76 (76.0)	2 (2.0)	22 (22.0)	0 (0.0)	1.46	0.83	BS
5.	Which Variety of English do you think you are good at?	91 (91.0)	9 (9.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1.18	0.57	BS
6.	What variety of English do you think other teachers use?	60 (60.0)	12 (12.0)	28 (28.0)	0 (0.0)	1.68	0.88	BS

Note: BS = British Standard, AE = American English, NE = Nigerian English, CO = Confused, RMK = Remark. NB: Numbers in parenthesis indicate percentage.

Table 4 above shows the variety of English language recommended and taught by teachers in secondary schools in Ekiti State. Most of the participants indicated that British Standard English is the recommended variety by the syllabus for teaching (88.0%), a small percentage (10.0%) indicated Nigerian English as the recommended variety, a very small percentage (2.0%) identified American English as recommended variety while percentage of those who are confused about the variety of English to be taught was 0.0%. Likewise, a larger percentage (90.0%) of the teachers indicated that

they teach British English in their classes, the remaining 10.0% indicated that they teach American English while none of the teachers teach Nigerian English or are not sure about the variety they teach. The question “Which variety do the examination bodies examine?” elicited 87.0% of participants indicating British English, a very small percentage (1.0%) indicated American English, only 12.0% indicated Nigerian English while no teacher is confused about the variety examined by examination bodies. As for the variety of English used outside the classroom, 76.0% teacher indicated that they

use British English, 2.0% use American English, a sizable percentage (22.0%) use Nigerian English while 0.0% is confused about the variety they use. Interestingly, in response to the question “Which variety of English do you think you are good at”, most of the teachers indicated that they are good at British English (91.0%), a small percentage (9.0%) are good at American English while none of the teachers indicated that they are good at Nigerian English or confused. When asked about the variety of English other teachers use, a large percentage (60.0%) indicated that other teachers use British English, about half of the percentage of those who selected British English choose Nigerian English as the variety other teachers use, a small percentage (12.0%) choose American English while no one is confused.

Research Question 4: What is the Level of Proficiency of Teachers in the British Standard English they Claim to Teach?

Table 6. Level of Proficiency of Teachers in the British Standard English

Score	Proficiency level	Frequency (%)
16-18	Proficient	6 (6.0%)
11-15	Advanced	1 (1.0%)
9-10	Intermediate	12 (12.0%)
6-8	Pre-intermediate	18 (18.0%)
1-5	Lower level	63 (63.0%)

Table 6 above shows the level of proficiency of teachers in the British Standard English. The table indicates that 63 (63.0%) teachers have lower-level proficiency in the British Standard English, 18 (18.0%) teachers have pre-intermediate level proficiency in the British Standard English, 12 (12.0%) teachers have intermediate level proficiency in the British Standard English, 1 (1.0%) teacher has advanced level proficiency in the British Standard English, while 6 (6.0%) teachers are considered proficient in the British Standard English.

Research Question 5: What is the Actual Variety of English the Teachers Use in Classroom Interaction?

The teachers were observed in the Classroom and the assessment sheets revealed that the teachers’ pronunciation and expressions are predominantly that of Nigerian English Variety, indicating a disparity between claimed proficiency and actual instructional language use. Comparing this with the variety checklist provided to test the actual variety been used and taught by the teachers in the class shows that show that majority of the teachers are confused about English variety. , 80 (80.0%) teachers considered “to eat one’s cake and have it” as British Standard English while 20 (20.0%) considered the expression as non-standard British English. In item 2, 52 (52.0%) teachers considered “beggars have no choice” as British Standard English while 48 (48.0%) considered the expression as non-standard British English. In item 3, 86 (86.0%) teachers considered “two sides of a coin” as British Standard English while 14 (14.0%) considered the expression as non-standard British English. In item 4, 81 (81.0%) teachers considered “woke up on the wrong side of the bed” as British Standard English while 19 (19.0%) considered the expression as non-standard British English. In item 5, 89 (89.0%) teachers considered “...take the laws into your hands” as British Standard English while 11 (11.0%) considered the expression as non-standard British English.

Discussion

The findings of the study on English language variety in Nigerian secondary schools present a complex and intriguing scenario regarding teacher proficiency, classroom instruction, and the use of different English varieties. At the outset, there's a clear discrepancy between the high percentages (95.0%) of teachers who believe they demonstrate proficiency in Standard English pronunciation, grammar, and vocabulary compared to the smaller proportion (5.0%) who acknowledge a lack of proficiency. This perception of high proficiency contrasts starkly with the proficiency test results which

reveal that a majority of teachers actually fall within lower proficiency levels in British Standard English.

Another intriguing aspect is the preference and confidence among teachers in their grasp of British English (91.0%) over American English (9.0%). However, the observation within classrooms indicates a predominantly different reality, with 99% of teachers using Nigerian English expressions and pronunciation while teaching various topics in English Grammar, pronunciation, Vocabulary and writing. This significant disparity between claimed proficiency and the actual language used in instruction suggests a potential mismatch or complexity in defining and implementing proficiency standards. This is an indication of a serious confusion in the English Language classrooms. Moreover, while a significant percentage of teachers claim to provide accurate and appropriate language models for their students (83.0%), a notable portion (17.0%) did not affirm this. This raises questions about the consistency and quality of language models being presented to students in the classroom, especially considering the prevalence of Nigerian English expressions in teaching.

The evident discrepancy between claimed proficiency, preferred English variety, and actual classroom instruction practices highlights several important implications. Firstly, it emphasizes the need for a nuanced understanding of language proficiency beyond self-assessment, considering the multifaceted nature of language varieties and their application in educational settings. Additionally, it underscores the importance of aligning teacher training and professional development with the linguistic realities of the classroom. Acknowledging and embracing the diversity of English varieties used in Nigeria's educational context could be vital in promoting effective communication and understanding among teachers and students.

Conclusion

The findings of this study have emphasized the complexity of language use, proficiency, and instructional practices in Nigerian secondary schools using Ekiti state as example. Addressing the disparity between perceived and actual proficiency levels, reconciling language variety preferences with classroom practices and enhancing teacher training to better cater to diverse linguistic needs could significantly contribute to more effective language instruction and communication within the educational system. The findings of this study highlight the importance of acknowledging and integrating diverse English varieties, including Nigerian English, into syllabi and instructional strategies to better cater for the linguistic needs of students. This position has affirmed the assertion of Babatunde (2002) that “there is a perceived problem in the English language pedagogy in Nigeria with the acclaimed British standard strictly recommended by the various examination bodies and syllabi and curricula”

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